

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Intonation Analysis in the context of Violin Education

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Supervisor: Nazif Can Tamer

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Abstract

In Western Classical music, notes are often viewed within a discrete spectrum based on the 12-tone equal temperament system (12-TET), and playing beyond this is considered “out of tune”. However, the existence of many other tuning systems makes the concept of ‘in-tune notes’ subjective and dependent on cultural background, timbre, and instrumentation. This is particularly evident in fretless violins, where precise intonation is essential. In this study, we aim to analyze intonation choices by violin instructors on a broad scale, focusing on deviations from the 12-TET due to tonality and hand positions, aiming to enhance intonation understanding and teaching insights. Utilizing an automatic music transcription model (MUSC) with higher resolution than 12-TET, we employ separate models for short and long notes to precisely segment pitch, considering intonation deviation and nuances.

We provide our results on the common violin teaching techniques using Wohlfahrt Op. 45’s 60 etudes, where seven players perform these monophonic, first-position etudes in seven major keys without accidentals. Findings indicate sharper intonation in the third and seventh degrees compared to 12-TET across tonalities; the first and fourth degrees align better with 12-TET, with the mediant (III) and leading tone (VII) being about 5 cents sharper above the tonic. This study highlights ways to improve the understanding of violin intonation choices, which could inspire more adequate teaching methods, bringing together tradition, technology, and cross-cultural appreciation.

Keywords: Intonation analysis; Violin; Music education; Intonation modelling

Chapter 1

Introduction

Listening to music involves a combination of different processes that result in unique cognitive experiences. When interacting with a musical performance, several elements contribute to how a listener perceives it as enjoyable or captivating. These elements include factors such as pitch, intonation, musicality, timing, dynamics, and more. Their impact can vary based on variables such as the type of instrument, timbre, register, accompaniment presence, and the melodic and harmonic context [1].

In the musical education field, has been conducted considerable research in the string technique and pedagogy areas [2], where many experts have done research looking for answers in the intonation domain. Although string education research is a very young field, every day string educators are asked to decide what's the best way to teach their students, adjusting its method to their specific needs. Most of the existing literature around classical violin deal with the main basic trouble that every string instrumentalist has to face since the very early days of their training: intonation and pitch assessment.

Regarding Western Classical music feature engineering-based methods, the usual tendency is to be as general as possible, instead of deriving performance metrics from pedagogy or instrument research. This leads to a non instrument-specific feedback on music essentials as pitch or timing [3]. In reality, posture and technique

are closely related to the instrument itself, and should be taken in consideration closely for performance assessment.

In the case of violin, it luckily has some kind of specific dedication as it is one of the most important instruments in Western Classical music, along with piano. That fact has been the seed of different research about performance assessment for pitch estimation, mostly using signal processing-based methods whose main goals may be intonation, note segmentation and vibrato analysis [4].

1.1 Motivation

Intonation is a critical issue for all musicians, and specially for string players. Intonation analysis is a field that has been studied for years with the same type of methodology, relying on very small sets of samples, and manual corrections and error solving.

Looking for patrons and models for violin intonation aims to have a better vision about the cognition mechanisms that make us feel in what context a sound is in or out of tune. There are lots of factors that can influence intonation, such as hand posture and pressure, notes surrounding the note of interest, key, mode, position, etc.

The establishment of some kind of model that would join the relationship between the pre-established intonation models and what listeners and players define as tuned might be the start point to new violin education technologies and the improvement point of many other existing ones.

Violin intonation modelling while being based on music pedagogy, using Etudes and Caprices audios as the starting point, allows to face intonation in an objective way, very similar as the assessment that a violin teacher does with a student.

The generated new knowledge in this field can also lead into further applications in general music education, music education technology, ethnomusicology, expressive performance analysis, symbolic music generation or musicological analysis, among

others. The generalization of this type of study can lead to changes in the way we actually understand and learn music.

1.2 Objectives & Structure of the Report

Given this, our objective is to model the violin intonation process in an objective way, using tools as pitch estimation and vibrato analysis following a pedagogical approach.

This research on large-scale intonation analysis aims to:

- Differentiate between intonation choice and error: understand the influence of musical context (direction, key, scale degree, etc.), physic or physiological causes.
- Find and model recurrent intonation issues related to psycho-acoustics that might have an implication in the way that humans listen to sounds and understand intonation and music.

All these objectives will hopefully open the door to very valuable and relevant concepts for musical education, ethnomusicology and expressive performance analysis.

1.3 Background

There are many different recognized methods for Western classical violin training: from Suzuki to Wohlfart, but also Mazas, Kreutzer, Kayser and Dancla, among many others. Using string pedagogy as the guideline, an in-depth study of several violinists playing this Wohlfart Opus 45 etudes will be done in order to differentiate any specific intonation and pitch relevant association between the violin technique and the pitch development of the player.

1.3.1 Intonation and tuning

Defining the differences between intonation and tuning will be fundamental to fully understand the related work among these areas. On the one hand, intonation may be defined as the pitch accuracy in singing or playing an instrument. On the other hand, tuning has a different meaning, considering a particular pitches set to which an instrument is tuned. As we can see, these are two different concepts that are closely related. In string instruments, being in tune is in fact the combination of them both, requiring a proper tuning and correct intonation. A correct tuning will be achieved by setting the strings at the proper note (in Western classical music, E-A-D-G with A=440Hz as a reference usually).

Authors like Hopkins or Platt & Racine [5, 6] have studied the acquisition of musical skills as the musicians' ability to tune their own instruments independently to a pitch standard. Some authors note that tuning is one of the most important and fundamental skills string players must have. The intervention and use of digital elements like visual electronic tuners may increase the efficiency of the tuning process but it's argued that the use of that type of devices may affect the capacity to develop the necessary aural skills.

A correct tuning is the base to develop a correct intonation. Proper intonation will be a matter of auditory expertise and ear training that string players have to deal with their whole career. It is usually related in literature with the different existing tuning systems: the Equally-tempered scale, Pythagorean tuning and Just

Intonation.

1.3.2 Different tuning and intonation systems

Intonation systems encompass the organization of pitches, intervals, and scales within a musical system, as well as the specific tuning standards and practices associated with a particular style or genre of music.

Very different intonation systems exist in music, each of them with unique and specific principles and rules. Every intonation system has its own characteristics, resulting in different strengths and weaknesses, and then different effects on music performance. The use of one intonation system or another will vary depending on the music style, instruments, the composer or performer preferences...

For the case of the violin, different authors have studied the tendencies of players towards one system or another, this is, studied the expansion or reduction of certain intervals with respect to their theoretical values in relation to the different systems [7].

Equal temperament

Equal temperament is a type of tuning system that approximates just intervals by dividing into equal steps an octave (or other intervals). The purpose of this system is to reduce the number of tones in the scale from frequency based on exact ratios to those which produce intervals. This system gives an equal perceived step size as the frequency ratio of any adjacent pair of notes will be the same, giving that pitch is perceived as the logarithm of frequency.

While in Western music this step is equal to 12 (twelve-tone equal temperament, 12-TET), it can vary depending on the culture and musical tradition, reaching values as high as 53 (53-TET) in the case of Turkish music and as low as five, seven or nine tone temperaments, used in instruments as Indonesian gamelas (5-TET) or Chinese music (7-TET), for example.

Figure 1: Equal temperament illustration, CC BY-SA 3.0 Wikipedia

12-Tone Equal Temperament (12-TET)

In Western music, the twelve-tone equal temperament (12-TET) is the most common tuning system since the 18th Century. This system divides the octave into 12 equal parts on a logarithmic scale. Their ratio is equal to the 12 root of 2, and the semitone (smallest interval) will be equal to the 1/12 of the width of an octave.

Pythagorean scale

A series of intervals devised to create a scale dividing the octave into more or less equal steps on the basis of powers of $2/3$ or $3/2$. This is based on the perfect 5th intervals tuned as the $3/2$ ratio. The ratios between successive steps are either the whole tone ($9/8$, 204 cents) or the diatonic semitone ($256/243$, 90 cents) [8]. The main disadvantage of this system is that it is impossible to arrive at an octave multiple of a note. For the given series:

$$2/3 \quad 1 \quad 3/2 \quad (3/2)^2 \quad (3/2)^3 \quad (3/2)^4 \quad (3/2)^5$$

The series of intervals in a Pythagorean scale will be the following:

$$1 \quad 9/8 \quad 81/64 \quad 4/3 \quad 3/2 \quad 27/16 \quad 243/128 \quad 2$$

If this series is extended with $(3/2)^6$ on the right and $(2/3)^6$ on the left we would obtain a chromatic scale of 12 tones.

Just Intonation

System that relies in the tuning of musical intervals as whole number ratios of frequencies, as found in the harmonic series, a ordered set of frequencies which are integer multiples of a fundamental and where the amplitude of each partial is inversely proportional to the partial number [8]. Just Intervals consist of tones from a single harmonic series of an implied fundamental.

1.3.3 Interactions and differences between intonation systems

Temperament refers to any system in which small interval tuning changes in a scale are introduced such that these intervals are no longer exact frequency ratios as in the Just Intonation or the Pythagorean scale. These last two systems share a characteristic that consists on the existing difference between a raised semitone (sharp) and a lowered semitone (flat). They are related by a $2187/2048$ interval (chromatic semitone) that assures that in cases of enharmonicity such as $C\#/D\flat$ the pitch is not the same.

The interval between the diatonic and chromatic semitone is called Pythagorean Comma. The relationship between the different intonation systems can be seen in the next page. It is possible to observe the difference between a sharp and a flat in the Pythagorean and Just Intonation.

It's important to note that certain intervals tend to be more similar between intonation systems than others. That is the case of the Perfect Fourth and Perfect Fifth, whose difference between 12-TET and Just Intonation is equal to 1.96 cents and -1.96 cents respectively. On the other hand, the most different intervals when comparing are the minor third and Major Sixth, whose difference reaches -15.64 cents and +15.64 cents, respectively. A comparison between the value in cents for every interval in twelve-tone equal temperament and Just Intonation can be seen in Figure 2 (at the end of the chapter).

Table 1: Comparison between 12-TET and Just Intonation

Interval name	12-TET	Cents	Just Intonation	Cents	Difference(cents)
Unison	$2^0 = 1$	0	1	0	0
Minor second	$2^{\frac{1}{12}} = \sqrt[12]{2}$	100	16/15	111.73	-11.73
Major second	$2^{\frac{2}{12}} = \sqrt[6]{2}$	200	9/8	203.91	-3.91
Minor third	$2^{\frac{3}{12}} = \sqrt[4]{2}$	300	6/5	315.64	-15.64
Major third	$2^{\frac{4}{12}} = \sqrt[3]{2}$	400	5/4	386.31	13.69
Perfect Fourth	$2^{\frac{5}{12}} = \sqrt[12]{32}$	500	4/3	498.04	1.96
Tritone	$2^{\frac{6}{12}} = \sqrt[2]{2}$	600	64/45	609.78	-9.78
Perfect Fifth	$2^{\frac{7}{12}} = \sqrt[12]{128}$	700	3/2	701.96	-1.96
Minor Sixth	$2^{\frac{8}{12}} = \sqrt[3]{4}$	800	8/5	813.69	-13.69
Major Sixth	$2^{\frac{9}{12}} = \sqrt[4]{8}$	900	5/3	884.36	15.64
Minor Seventh	$2^{\frac{10}{12}} = \sqrt[6]{32}$	1000	16/9	996.09	3.91
Major Seventh	$2^{\frac{11}{12}} = \sqrt[12]{2048}$	1100	15/8	1088.27	11.73
Octave	$2^{\frac{12}{12}} = 2$	1200	2/1	1200	0

As we can see, the table is symmetric in cents difference around the Tritone. The sign of this difference varies in mirror from the center value corresponding to the Tritone for each symmetric value.

Note	Pythagorean		Just Intonation		Equal Temperament	
	Frequency	Cents	Frequency	Cents	Frequency	Cents
C	1	0	1	0	1	0
C [♯]	$\frac{2187}{2048}$	114	$\frac{25}{24}$	71	$2^{1/12}$	100
D ^b	$\frac{256}{243}$	89	$\frac{16}{15}$	112		
D	$\frac{9}{8}$	204	$\frac{9}{8}$	204	$2^{1/6}$	200
D [♯]	$\frac{19683}{16384}$	317	$\frac{75}{64}$	275	$2^{1/4}$	300
E ^b	$\frac{32}{27}$	294	$\frac{6}{5}$	316		
E	$\frac{81}{64}$	409	$\frac{5}{4}$	386	$2^{1/3}$	400
E [♯]	$\frac{177147}{131072}$	522	$\frac{125}{96}$	457		
F ^b	$\frac{8192}{6561}$	385	$\frac{32}{25}$	427		
F	$\frac{4}{3}$	498	$\frac{4}{3}$	498	$2^{5/12}$	500
F [♯]	$\frac{729}{512}$	612	$\frac{45}{32}$	590	$2^{1/2}$	600
G ^b	$\frac{1024}{729}$	588	$\frac{36}{25}$	631		
G	$\frac{3}{2}$	702	$\frac{3}{2}$	702	$2^{7/12}$	700
G [♯]	$\frac{6561}{4096}$	816	$\frac{25}{16}$	773	$2^{2/3}$	800
A ^b	$\frac{128}{81}$	792	$\frac{8}{5}$	814		
A	$\frac{27}{16}$	906	$\frac{5}{3}$	884	$2^{3/4}$	900
A [♯]	$\frac{59049}{32768}$	1019	$\frac{225}{128}$	977	$2^{5/6}$	1000
B ^b	$\frac{16}{9}$	996	$\frac{9}{5}$	1018		
B	$\frac{243}{128}$	1109	$\frac{15}{8}$	1088	$2^{11/12}$	1100
B [♯]	$\frac{531441}{262144}$	1228	$\frac{125}{64}$	1159		
C [♯]	$\frac{4096}{2187}$	1086	$\frac{48}{25}$	1129		
C	2	1200	2	1200	2	1200

Figure 2: Comparison between tuning systems [8]

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Intonation analysis requires either manual annotations for frequency and notes or automatic methods for their extraction, as it is related to the extent to which the performed pitch deviates from note centers in equal temperament. The approach we chose in this thesis involves automatic methods; therefore, we represent and review the following three fields of study, focusing on their relation to large-scale intonation analysis:

First, some of the most representative algorithms for pitch estimation and vibrato analysis are presented. After that, the work surrounding intonation analysis will be summarized, taking into account different contributions about contextual variables such as accompaniment type, vibrato, or direction.

2.1 Pitch estimation and monophonic transcription

Different pitch estimation algorithms are considered and used to analyze the time-varying waveform of an audio signal and extract the dominant frequency components to estimate the pitch. Computational methods for monophonic pitch estimation have been studied for a long time [9], reaching reliable methods that include the auto-correlation function (ACF) [10], the normalized cross-correlation function (NCCF) proposed by RAPT [11] and also by PRAAT [12] or the cepstrum [9], among others.

The existence of neural networks like CREPE [13] or TAPE [14] allow to estimate pitch in a simpler but also more reliable way.

CREPE

CREPE is a pitch tracking algorithm that utilizes a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) to estimate the fundamental frequency of a monophonic audio signal [13]. The CNN operates directly on the time-domain waveform, taking a 1024-sample excerpt with a 16 kHz sampling rate as input. The architecture consists of six convolutional layers, resulting in a 2048-dimensional latent representation. This latent representation is then densely connected to an output layer with sigmoid activations, producing a 360-dimensional output vector. The pitch estimate is determined deterministically based on this output vector.

The authors evaluated CREPE using two datasets: RWC-synth, which consists of synthesized audio with a fixed number of sinusoids, and MDB-stem-synth, which contains more realistic monophonic audio tracks re-synthesized with perfect pitch annotations.

The findings indicate that CREPE demonstrates an exceptionally high level of accuracy in estimating pitch, particularly when examining its performance on the RWC-synth dataset. In this regard, CREPE significantly outperformed both pYIN [15] and SWIPE [16] by a substantial margin. Furthermore, when assessing its efficacy on the more varied MDB-stem-synth dataset, CREPE continues to exhibit superior accuracy and resilience, particularly in handling intricate timbral nuances, when compared to the baseline algorithms.

Additionally, the authors conducted evaluations of the algorithmic performance under various levels of additive noise, revealing that CREPE excels particularly well in scenarios characterized by low signal-to-noise ratios.

MUSC

MUSC is the proposed multistream conformer for music that processes the raw audio waveform required as input (sampled at 44.1kHz) into four different streams, which include onset, offset, semitone-level frames, and high-resolution f0 frames, with a frame rate of 5.8ms. The resulting outputs can be used for both frame-level dataset annotation for training and MIDI transcription with pitch bends.

The model employs audio-to-score alignment (ASA) to allow AMT while representing pitch deviations as vibrato, glissando, or intonation choices, incorporating fine-grained pitch representation into transcription [17]. This model also allows frame-level annotations for violin transcription, considering simultaneous transcription and alignment in a joint framework, improving the alignment quality in an expectation-maximization strategy, and incorporating onset-based features.

MUSC uses labels generated by TAPE [14], an end-to-end timbre-aware pitch estimator that eliminates the need for a source separation step before estimating the pitch of the target source.

CREPE Notes

Crepe Notes constitutes a new method for post-processing CREPE's output to achieve monophonic note segmentation [18]. With a 97% reduction in the total number of parameters used when compared with other deep learning based methods and state-of-the-art results, this model processes raw audio samples using a convolutional neural network (CNN) to predict an f0 value for every 10ms of a given piece of audio.

This method combines additional information with pitch contours to increase the accuracy of the output. It uses the principles of pitch change by more than a semitone to demarcate note boundaries. The method also considers vocal-specific features such as phoneme boundaries and statistical models applied to pitch contours.

Several post-processing steps are involved to improve the segmentation of the notes. These steps include detecting note onsets using an onset detection algorithm, con-

verting f0 estimates to semitone units, and adjusting note boundaries based on amplitude and f0 gradient.

The method was evaluated on two datasets: one containing jazz saxophone solos, and the other containing traditional Irish flute recordings. It outperformed other systems on these datasets, demonstrating its effectiveness for solo instrumental transcription tasks and achieving state-of-the-art results.

2.2 Vibrato analysis

When discussing intonation analysis for violin, it will be necessary to separate the intonation choices from the vibrato effects for a reliable output.

The boundaries between intonation and vibrato analysis are blurred because vibrato is a controlled and periodic oscillation in pitch [19]. It is not rare that the tools developed for intonation analysis as YIN or time-domain pitch estimation techniques as the McLeod Pitch Method [20], among others, are often helpful for its analysis, in addition to the existence of specific models.

Template-based vibrato analysis

This type of approach, presented at the ISMIR Conference 2016, aims to perform the analysis directly on a signal's spectrogram representation, where characteristic spectrotemporal patterns make vibrato evident. The detection and parameterization of the patterns are obtained by comparing the predefined set of vibrato templates to the spectrogram, achieving a more robust approach than F0-based strategies for the systematic experiments performed by researchers at the time [21].

Pitch contour-based vibrato analysis

Essentia, one of the most popular libraries for audio analysis and audio-based music information retrieval, contains an extensive collection of reusable algorithms, among which it is possible to find a vibrato algorithm that detects the presence of vibrato and estimates its parameters, given a pitch contour [22].

Its outputs are the estimated vibrato frequency [Hz] and estimated vibrato extent [cents]. It is an extended version of the vocal vibrato detection in *Predominant-Melody* and should be given the outputs of a pitch estimator (*PredominantMelody*, *PitchYinFFT*, *PitchMelodia*, for example) and the corresponding sample rate [23].

2.3 Intonation analysis related work

On the field of study of intonation and tuning, recent studies have researched their characteristics and the different contextual variables that could affect the perception of pitch and what is perceived as 'in tune'[1, 24]. Among these factors is possible to find:

- Instrument type
- Melodic and harmonic context
- Solo performance or accompaniment presence
- Accompaniment type
- Timbre
- Register
- Vibrato use

2.3.1 Instrument-related differences

It has been studied whether non-absolute pitch listeners can accurately judge the intonation of completely isolated notes. The results suggest that both musicians and non-musicians are able to recognize absolute intonation when listening to familiar timbres such as piano or violin [25]. However, only musicians displayed marginally stronger proof of absolute intonation identification when tested with unfamiliar tones like triangle and inverted sine waves. Familiarity with the timbre may have an impact on one's capacity to detect absolute intonation.

Regarding wind instruments, Duke didn't find any significant differences among intervals regarding overall deviation [26]. The project consisted on 48 musicians, that performed, both melodically and harmonically and in both ascending and descending directions, four diatonic intervals (major third, perfect fourth, perfect fifth, and major sixth). Some significant tendencies related to direction were found as intervals were slightly sharper when descending and slightly flatter while ascending.

2.3.2 Related factors for violin and the string family

Objective performance analysis has been researched in order to provide some insights into the expressive character of a performance and the unique qualities of each performance and player [27]. It allows the measurement and comparison of musical performances micro-structure, which could be the key to reveal differences between them.

Multiple studies regarding string education and performance analysis have been done with the objective of understanding better the deviations from the previously mentioned tuning and intonation systems.

Intonation is not an absolute concept, and in the case of violin, most of the time Pythagorean system is used when playing any melody, scale or passage with only one line of music, as it will sound cleaner [7]. Just intonation is, according to expert violinists, generally preferred for double stops, but these two systems are not usually compatible and choices have to be made in order to assure a clean in tune performance. A good example of the compromise between committing to different intonation systems could be the Niccolò Paganini Caprice for Solo Violin, Op. 1 No. 13, where is necessary to play runs in double stops. The top line should be kept in Pythagorean intonation and adjust each lower note of the thirds according to Just Intonation to assure that each double stop is in tune while not losing the sense of direction and expression of the scale.

Intonation analysis for solo violin

A number of researchers have noted a general tendency to perform with sharp rather than flat deviation in many contexts, particularly for older, more experienced musicians [28]. Research has repeatedly indicated that the perception of sharpness is less accurate than flatness discrimination, particularly for old more musically experienced subjects [29].

In 1937, Greene analyzed five intervals (major and minor seconds, major and minor thirds and perfect fourths) played by six unaccompanied violinists [30]. He found that they typically performed in neither the natural nor the equally tempered scale; while major seconds and major thirds tended to be expanded, minor seconds and minor thirds tended to be contracted and perfect fourths tended to the theoretical scale values for the said interval. Although the players performed in neither scale, they agreed in the deviation's direction from ET with minor deviations. The average magnitude of each of the five intervals closely matched their theoretical extent in Pythagorean tuning.

Loosen stated that attempting to match data from live violin performances to theoretical intonation systems might not be meaningful, as in daily performances, violinists never play in one tuning or another [31]. He studied eight professional violinists that played three adjacent C Major scales without stopping and in ascending order (from C4 to C7) followed by an analogous scale in descending order to the initial note, C4. These scales were played very slowly and without vibrato to try to be as accurate as possible. These experiment results indicate that just intonation doesn't fit the data as well as Pythagorean or Equally tempered scales when the performances are analyzed taking into consideration the context of the scale. This study also stated that when C Major scales are played "the tonic is adopted as an absolute cognitive reference point" [31].

More recently, Geringer et al.(2018) [32] explored the intonation performances of eight highly regarded concert violinists from different generations (Heifetz, Grumiaux, Milstein, Perlman, Hahn, Midori, Barton Pine and Shaham) in an unaccompanied

context, playing two Bach pieces, one in D minor and other one in E Major. The study aims to understand how these performers deviate from equal temperament and whether these deviations are musically meaningful. The study found that the eight concert violinists deviated from equal temperament in musically meaningful ways, while they found own individual tendencies. Performances of the third and sixth scale degrees in the major and minor keys, which illustrate the largest tuning differences between systems, tended towards Pythagorean tuning. The deviations were consistent across repetitions of the same pitch, indicating that they may have been intentional.

Intonation analysis under different accompaniment types

As mentioned previously, intonation is not an absolute concept, as we always listen to it like something relative to the other sounds that we are hearing at the same time. That is the one of the reasons why the accompaniment type in a musical piece plays a very important role.

Piano is one of the most important types of accompaniment instruments for violin. Acoustic pianos are usually tuned with the octave slightly widened, approximating to equal temperament. They are the one instrument where fourths and fifths are not perfectly in tune, when generally for a string player that intervals are the ones where they're certain about as their difference between intonation systems is minimal. For all these reasons it's essential for violin to tune directly with the piano.

While playing in an ensemble, the intonation system have also been researched. Nickerson [33] attempted to test earlier findings that ensemble tuning was expected by Pythagorean tuning rather than equal-tempered tuning. Consistent with Greene's results on intonation tendencies for accompanied violinists [30], he reported sharper thirds and sixths than expected in equal-tempered tuning, and sharper solo performances than the ensemble performances. The major thirds and sixths were closest to the size expected in Pythagorean tuning.

In 1978, a study by Geringer et al. was performed on ninety-six undergraduate and graduate music students that either performed a second time or listened to their

individual performances and re-tuned them using a variable-speed tape recorder, following differential verbal feedback. Based on the study, there was a noticeable tendency towards sharp intonation compared to the standard of equal temperament. The differences between performance and perception depended on the accompaniment and scale degree. It was observed that intonation perception of unaccompanied scales was less accurate compared to both accompanied scale perception and performance conditions of unaccompanied and accompanied scales [29].

In 2013, Geringer et al. studied four recordings of Suzuki Violin School Volume I. In these performances, being one of the most recommended model for beginning string students, it was studied whether if they followed a theoretical tuning system like Pythagorean tuning or equal temperament (ET) or not, by examining the first eight measures and the repeat of Minuet I in G-major by Bach. The analysis revealed individual note deviations variations from -17 cents to +26 cents in relation with the accompaniment, although most of the variations were minor. Ultimately, no performer adhered consistently to either tuning system throughout the excerpt, while three performers tended to be closer to Pythagorean tuning and one performer was closer to equal temperament. Two performers were found to be consistently sharp in certain intervals, particularly minor seconds and thirds, as well as major thirds, regardless of the tuning system [28].

Among other types of accompaniments, we can find the drone, which has been pointed out as an effective technique for improving intonation, especially for scales and arpeggios. A positive to moderate relationship was found between using a drone accompaniment and improving intonation in fast passages, slow passages, and solo repertoire [34]. Having a constant intonation reference agrees with the general technique on looking for vibrating sympathetic strings to provide confirmation that they are playing the pitches accurately [35].

Vibrato

Although some violinists may say otherwise, vibrato is mainly used as an expressive tool rather than a way to camouflage out-of-tune notes. Its frequency and amplitude may vary depending on the kind of emotion the performer wants to transmit. Some studies have tried to study the relationship between vibrato modulation frequency and contextual parameters such as pitch, duration and tempo, as well as the performing artist in the case study of woodwind and brass solos in jazz recordings. No significant correlations between modulation frequency and pitch, duration, nor tempo were found [36].

Indeed, vibrato on the violin is seen as a direct imitation, along with the fingers, of the vibrato performed by singers [37]. Vibrato in violin and cello was compared in a group of 40 violinists and cellists in 2004. They performed an eight-measure passage with and without vibrato, whose analysis showed that the average rate of vibrato was around 5.5 Hz, and there were no significant differences between the instruments or the performer's skill level. It was observed that the violinists tended to play at a sharper pitch than the cellists, both with vibrato and without, being greater the width of the violin vibratos too. It was found that stability was gained while using vibrato. The performers alternated between pitch oscillations above and below the conceived pitch, rather than oscillating only above or below [38].

The perception of mistuned intervals in unaccompanied melodies and the differences could be altered whether vibrato is used or not. It's has been found that for different timbres, stimuli were perceived as more out of tune when there was no vibrato compared to vibrato [1].

Melodic context: Direction

As we have seen in previous articles mentioned above, direction is a factor to be taken into account in the study of intonation. This subject has also been dealt with from the perspective of the social psychology of music. Our natural inclination is to start a scale from the lower notes, not the higher ones, and we typically end it on a

lower note as well. Some authors like Farnsworth [39] suggest that the act of rising creates a feeling of tonal decline, while falling gives off the impression of approach.

Studies like Sogin's [40] show that, while all stringed instruments perform sharp relative to equal temperament, descending pitch sets are significantly sharper than ascending pitch sets. Geringer's results on intonational performance and perception of ascending scales [29] found a tendency toward sharp intonation when performing and perceiving ascending scales, compared to the standard of equal temperament.

2.3.3 Intonation modeling in music teaching

According to Dickey's 1992 review [41], various types of modeling in music classes can effectively communicate concepts, with modeling often being more effective than verbal descriptions. To be effective, teachers need to have skills in both correct and incorrect modeling.

In a series of investigations [42, 43, 44], Goolsby found that experienced teachers dedicated over twice the amount of time to non-verbal demonstrations and modeling compared to their younger counterparts. Additionally, Sang discovered a strong correlation between teachers' modeling skills, time spent modeling, and student performance levels [45].

2.3.4 General tendencies among the consulted bibliography

As we can note, several studies regarding intonation on violin have been performed. Although the results might differ on some points from one to another, the general knowledge is to note the sharper deviation from the selected intonation references for Western Classical Music (12-TET). Particularly on seconds and thirds (major and minor)[30], and, in general, thirds and sixths [28, 38], acknowledging violin tuning to be closest to Pythagorean tuning sizes [30, 33, 38]. Direction results might be a little controversial as some authors defend that ascending sequences are associated with sharper intonation [29] while others defend that that is the case of descending sequences [40].

Chapter 3

Datasets

To provide a comprehensive and detailed understanding of the workflow implemented in this project, we will provide an in-depth description of the dataset that was used. This will give a clear perspective of the analyzed data, and how it relates to the overall objectives of the project.

3.1 Violin Etudes Dataset

Western classical music has created teaching curricula to guide the students for success in their musical education. Etudes are study pieces that present some kind of technical, musical or physiological problem or challenge in the context of a musical setting that requires proper study and correct interpretation [46, 47].

In the field of MIR, etudes and caprices provide a favorable type of dataset as they are often written for solo instruments and also, there are highly known and accessible for anybody that looks for teaching material, then, supporting deep learning applications.

Music pedagogy guided the violin etudes dataset included in 'High resolution violin transcription using weak labels' [17] by Tamer et al. which we are going to use in this work. This dataset is a collection of Etude Methods that features various classical composers formed by Kayser 36 Etudes for violin Op. 20, Wohlfahrt 60

Studies for Violin Op. 45 and Paganini 24 Caprices Op.1, which are included in the Violin Etudes dataset [48].

This dataset follows a pedagogical approach, being collected from YouTube videos by querying method/etude names, after identifying reliable content creators. This approach makes working for analysis at large scale way more accessible, allowing the use of deep learning models as MUSC [17].

3.1.1 Wohlfahrt Op45 etudes subset

After considering all the pieces contained in the mentioned dataset, a series of etudes has been selected from the different methods, considering seven Major key, monophonic etudes with no position changes and no accidentals from Wohlfahrt Op45. The lack of accidentals assures no modulation during the course of the music, while knowing that the fingering of the notes is restricted to only first position.

This Wohlfahrt Op45 etude subset comprehends the following music pieces played by a maximum of 7 violin players:

Table 2: Wohlfahrt Op45 etude selection comparison

Etude No	Tonality	Players	Main figure	Accidentals	Total note number
No 1	C Major	7	8th note	0	217
No 3	G Major	6	16th note	0	237
No 5	F Major	7	8th note	0	187
No 10	A Major	4	16th note	0	125
No11	Eb Major	6	16th note	2	223
No 15	C Major	7	16th note	0	505
No 26	G Major	7	8th note	0	240

The distribution of notes per etude and tonality can be found in the next page (Tables 3, 4 and 5). After applying the different methods described in the following methodology section (Chapter 4), we will obtain a single intonation deviation value per note. These values will be distributed into scale degrees, taking into consideration the tonality of the etude they come from.

Table 3: Number of notes per scale degree for the selected Wohlfahrt etudes

	No1	No3	No5	No10	No11	No15	No26
I	58	40	31	21	42	79	56
II	22	32	22	16	32	84	21
III	27	47	35	19	43	78	66
IV	13	35	28	19	26	62	16
V	34	39	29	19	35	68	60
VI	18	24	17	16	20	64	19
VII	45	20	25	15	23	70	2

Table 4: Number of notes per tonality

	C Major	G Major	F Major	A Major	Eb Major
I	137	96	31	21	42
II	106	53	22	16	32
III	105	113	35	19	43
IV	75	51	28	19	26
V	102	99	29	19	35
VI	82	43	17	16	20
VII	115	22	25	15	23

Considering the contribution of all players per etude, the final number of notes per tonality will be the following:

Table 5: Total number of notes per tonality (all players)

	C Major	G Major	F Major	A Major	Eb Major
I	959	632	217	84	252
II	742	339	154	64	192
III	735	744	245	76	258
IV	525	322	196	76	156
V	714	654	203	76	210
VI	574	277	119	64	120
VII	805	134	175	60	138

The number of accidentals will depend on the key: C Major will have no accidentals, while G Major and F Major will have 1 (one sharp on F and 1 flat on B, respectively) and A Major and Eb Major will have three, placing sharps on F, C and G, for A Major and flats on B, E and A, for Eb Major, respectively.

Chapter 4

Methods

Large scale intonation analysis requires to apply different pitch estimation and vibrato analysis techniques to obtain reliable discrete data. This data will then allow to perform a large scale study of the intonation through a pedagogically-oriented dataset of classical violin etudes.

Special attention will be given to note segmentation algorithms in order to achieve reliable intonation extraction. As intonation is heavily related to vibrato, it will be necessary to be able to disentangle the part dedicated to vibrato from intonation in general. Different models and algorithms have been used and considered in order to correctly assess the audio database used for this experiment.

4.1 Preprocessing for pitch estimates and alignments

The automatic music transcription (AMT) model introduced in [17] by Tamer et al. (MUSC) is used to process the original audio files, so higher frequency resolution than the conventional 12-TET can be achieved in violin transcription.

The required inputs for this model will be the raw audio file and its corresponding score in a MIDI format, to enable learning from weak labels. This allows the model to create initial audio-score alignments using music synchronization techniques.

In this procedure onset and offset energy levels will be taken into consideration, just as score information, to make the note segmentation process trustworthy and reliable. The pre-processed data obtained as output in a MIDI format will be used for the intonation analysis in the next steps of this work.

4.2 Pitch bend representations

After using MUSC on the selected etudes methods, we obtain one MIDI file per each etude played by each one of the seven selected players.

In each file is possible to consult the value of the pitch bends for each one of the notes, with a sample rate of 5.8ms, thanks to libraries as `pretty_midi`. `Pretty_midi` contains utility functions and classes for handling MIDI data so that it is in a format from which it is easy to modify and extract information [49].

Classes as "Note", "Instrument" and "PitchBend" have been indispensable for carrying out this work, as well as the included utility functions "key_number_to_key_name" or "note_number_to_hz", among others. In the next figure is possible to observe the different notes with their corresponding pitch bends.

Figure 3: Etude piano roll detail

These pitch bends will be the features in which we will rely to identify vibrato, glissando and any other type of intonation choice as they are fully independent from the notes' intonation sinusoid wave itself, so they only show the variations that differ from perfect intonation.

4.3 Modeling violin notes

Violin is a very analog instrument. Various factors can affect the pitch of played notes, including bow pressure, bow speed, hand placement, finger strength, and ornaments like glissando or vibrato. To investigate modeling options based on the available data, we have opted for a clustering-based methodology that can offer diverse insights.

One of the main topics that we have taken into consideration in this project has been note duration. It's very different to play a really short note (as a 16th note) than a longer one (a quarter note or similar), we're distinguishing the method we use to obtain reliable intonation information from both short and long notes.

The distinction of long and short notes carries an implicit question: where should be the boundary between them? After analyzing various etudes and cases, we have identified two key approaches: distinguishing elements among notes with different duration and scrutinizing the score.

Following this first idea, we made use of the `tslearn` library [50], which will help us to perform clustering according to the shapes of the different pitch bends of each note. We consider two different methods from `tslearn.clustering`: `TimeSeriesKMeans` and `KShape`.

- `tslearn.clustering.TimeSeriesKMeans`, designed for K-means clustering on time-series data, provides several parameters and attributes for configuring and analyzing the clustering process as the cluster and iteration numbers, random state or the labels, cluster centers and inertia. Short-note interpolation is performed so that all pitch bends have the same number of samples, and the

clustering will be smoother.

- `tslearn.clustering.KShape`, originally introduced in 2015, is a dedicated time series clustering algorithm [51]. It uses a normalized version of the cross-correlation measure to consider the shapes of the time series while comparing them. This method requires a dataset of equal-sized time series, so interpolation of the short notes is performed.

After testing `TimeSeriesKMeans` and `KShape`'s results, a clearer vision of the note clusters and shapes will be provided by `TimeSeriesKMeans`, which will be used instead of `KShape`. By organizing all the existing pitch bends (before the trimming algorithm for a more general vision) into duration groups and increasing the duration by 20ms in each group, our goal was to find elements to help differentiate different types of notes by duration; for example, the first duration group in which it is possible to find vibrato.

Figure 4: Clusters for Wohlfahrt Op45 etude selection for 160-180ms notes

In the previous figure we can see the influence of the bow pressure into the string in the tuning of very short notes, between 160 and 180ms of duration, but not any other type of sign that allow us to decide how to sort notes into different duration groups.

After clustering different etude notes we've come to the conclusion that around 220 to 240ms is the first time duration where we are able to see proper vibrato shapes.

Figure 5: Clusters for Wohlfahrt Op45 etude selection for 220-240ms notes

Vibrato is an ornamental resource that precisely tries to play with the intonation in a regular way in order to achieve a specific effect. Because of the way in which this ornamental technique is usually performed and its habitual use in classical music, it is possible to associate vibrato with notes of longer duration, not necessarily notes that last more than a certain duration, but that are being emphasised, being able to look for a new criterion to define the border between short and long notes.

This type of behavior has been observed for this etude collection as well as for other collections such as Kayser Op20, where 220-240ms was found to be the goal duration section to see the first vibrato shapes too.

For this specific case, the Wohlfahrt Op45 etudes we are considering are really steady, we can see that in all the scores there are notes of the same duration except for the last one, which will always be a little longer.

The fact that all the notes except for the last one have theoretically the same duration while in reality their duration varies from a minimum of 0.0227s in Brian Clement's No15 etude interpretation to a maximum of 0.743s in Tim Rowher's No11 etude, made us withdraw the first hypothesis we sustained for the division of notes into two duration groups at 0.24s, opting for the second one. We understand that even though all the notes should be equal, motor and cognitive patterns might be affecting the way the different artists play this type of notes, so their duration ends up being affected.

Our second hypothesis consists on a score-informed decision. As we mentioned, all the notes except for the last one are the same musical figure, so we will consider short notes all those that are not the last one, and this last one will be considered long note.

Figure 6: Clusters for Wohlfahrt etudes' last notes

Targeting needs of short and long violin notes

As we can see, different models are needed:

- For short notes, intonation is altered by the bowing movement inertia that is stabilized later on as the note advances.
- For the long notes, vibrato playing style will result in sinusoidal clusters, as we can see in Figure 6.

To capture intonation changes in the absence of vibrato and other ornaments, a vibrato model is introduced in the following chapters. This model enables the separation of vibrato from the main note intonation deviation, resulting in more accurate intonation measurements.

4.3.1 Modeling short notes

Note segmentation is a really important topic that has been deeply researched [52, 53]. For this matter, we need very reliable intonation deviation information. The MUSC model takes into consideration onset and offset energy levels, just as score information. This brings reliability to the pitch segmentation process. The achieved intonation deviation information will be taken into account in the form of pitch bends.

After plotting each pitch bend individually, we were able to see important changes on the pitch deviation at the very beginning and end of the pitch bends. In order to have a more general view we have made use of the `tslearn` library [50], whose `tslearn.clustering.TimeSeriesKMeans` algorithm will help us to do a clustering according to the shapes of the different pitch bends of each note.

Figure 7: Short notes clusters for Wohlfahrt etude selection

It's possible to see that the influence of the bow pressure into the string in the tuning of short notes is really high, adding a sudden peak at the beginning of the vast majority of pitch bends. Sudden peaks might also be seen at the end of some pitch bends as the result of changes in the bow direction or bow pressure.

The main goal is to analyze the pitch bends in order to take into consideration their most stable part. Sudden changes at the beginning and end of the pitch bends will be removed by the note segmentation algorithm that we have created for this specific purpose.

This peak-detection oriented algorithm looks for the most stabilized zone of every note. It will take advantage of the SciPy library peak detection functions [54]. The peak detection function (`scipy.signal.find_peaks`) takes a 1-D array and finds all local maxima by simple comparison of neighboring values. A subset of these peaks might be selected specifying peak conditions and properties as height, threshold, distance, prominence or width.

As the peak-detection oriented algorithm depends on the shape of each note's pitch bend, we have linked this approach to the clustering of the existing notes for a better performance, allowing us to see in more depth the most common types of pitch bend curves.

The algorithm avoids sudden sharp peaks, looking for the most stabilized zone, where peaks are more alike and tend to be in a similar cents intonation deviation (y-axis) range, allowing a better vision about intonation for every note. The term coverage will be introduced to be able to control the percentage remaining of the analyzed time series after the action of the algorithm. As it depends on the shape of every note, the coverage will be different for every note, player and etude. The mean coverage overall for all short notes, all players and etudes after the use of this algorithm will be 66.79% .

Working with the stabilized section

Once we achieve the identification of an stable region for each pitch bend of each note, we will calculate the histogram of each pitch bend. In that way we can know the number of times that each pitch deviation value was repeated, and take into consideration the weights of each of the considered values in order to translate the stable time series into a general intonation deviation value that represents each pitch bend.

We will analyze the counts of values in the histogram bins and take the value of bin with the maximum count value. In the case that more than one bin had the same count value, the mean index value of the bins will be performed.

Figure 8: Histogram example for the pitch bend

For this pitch bend example, we can see that for the stable selected part of the pitch bend (Figure 8, left, in red), there are three main predominant bins in its correspondent histogram (Figure 8, right): 9.42382812, 10.10742188 and 9.75195312. As they have the same count value the mean of the values is performed, being 9.761 cents the final mean result for the stabilized section of this pitch bend.

After applying this process to all the pitch bends for all players, the corresponding stabilized values for each note will be organized and analyzed, grouping them into the corresponding scale degrees for each etude and tonality.

4.3.2 Modeling long notes

In the case of long notes, the sudden peaks that we have previously observed in short notes can also be noted both at the beginning and at the end of pitch bends. In most cases, they will be camouflaged or added to the influence of ornaments such as vibrato, which can be detected in all the of longer duration notes that we have observed.

For these notes, the segmentation algorithm will also be used alongside with a custom vibrato model, that after being tested with Wohlfahrt Op45 and Kayser Op20 etude collections, will serve to obtain the necessary information about the tonal stability of each of the notes with greater length.

Vibrato model

When plotting some notes pitch bends is possible to see a well-distinguished wave-form that may indicate the existence of a defined vibrato. This usually happens in the last notes of the etudes which are usually associated with a longer duration and a very attractive vibrato, but it is not only restricted to those.

Figure 9: Pitch events in one of long note example after segmentation

This type of intonation variation led us to think of a way of characterizing every one of these notes with a model that has increasingly gained in difficulty.

The mission of the vibrato model is to capture the intonation changes in long notes without the interference of the vibrato. The reconstruction of the vibrato allows us to separate that ornament from the main long-note intonation deviation, so that we can use this last information in our study.

The most basic model for characterizing vibrato included:

- Start time
- End time
- Static mean intonation value
- Static amplitude intonation value
- Frequency of the wave

Thanks to the tslearn K-means clustering on time-series algorithms [50] we have been able to cluster different notes with vibrato in order to identify the different shapes present in our sample. The following plot shows the different obtained clusters for notes longer than 1 second in the Kayser Op.20 method, for all players. We chose this set of etudes as it includes different types of scores that don't specifically have to have the same length and it's easier to find notes with well-defined vibrato which is usually associated to longer notes. Clusters may have different scales in an attempt to better visualize their shape.

Figure 10: Vibrato note clustering for more than 1s long notes in Kayser Op20

As it is possible to see, in the 30 clusters there is a variety of rates but also amplitudes and shapes, having some clusters with notes that have no apparent vibrato also, i.e. cluster number 7. It is important to note the shape of clusters 8, 13 and 24 as the amplitude increases leaving a peak vibrato in the middle of the note. Amplitude, rate and mean vary with time for vibrato, and this happens to all notes played with this type of ornament.

Thanks to this detailed study, later on, time-varying amplitude and mean of the intonation were added to the model we had already developed, resulting on a model that included:

- Start time
- End time
- Time-varying mean intonation value (vibrato center) [cents]
- Time-varying amplitude intonation value (vibrato amplitude) [cents]
- Frequency of the wave (vibrato rate) [Hz]

Frequency computation

The frequency will be computed via rFFT, allowing us to see all the frequency components of each signal.

Figure 11: rFFT example for one note

Time-varying mean and amplitude intonation algorithm

In order to get an accurate approximation to the instantaneous mean change of the mean and the amplitude, an envelope-based algorithm was constructed. One upper envelope and one lower envelope, constructed by interpolating between peaks on the signal will be the ones allowing the time variance.

Figure 12: Envelope example for one note

This approach assures that the variation in amplitude will have a sample rate of 5.8ms, being able not just to know the amplitude by subtracting the upper and lower envelope, but also calculate the time-varying mean value of the vibrato and being able to know the shape of the vibrato itself.

This model allows us to actually reconstruct vibrato and create a very close sinusoid for every specific vibrato with a simple formula:

$$\text{sinusoid} = \text{mean} + \text{amplitude} * \sin(2 * \pi * \text{frequency} * t + \text{phase_shift})$$

A first look at the possibilities of this model will give us reconstructions like the following graph. This approach uses the envelopes to compute amplitude but not in a continuous way.

Figure 13: Comparison between vibrato and the reconstructed sinusoid with constant mean

Then, time-varying mean and amplitude will be introduced, allowing this kind of graph:

Figure 14: Comparison between original vibrato signal and the reconstructed sinusoid with time-varying mean and amplitude

As it is possible to see, as the phase is not taken into consideration, the waves are not exactly the same, but this is a meditated decision. Although this model can serve as a model for vibrato reconstruction, which may be of influence for fields such as music generation, for the ultimate purpose for which it will be used in this work, the phase will be deliberately omitted since what we are looking for is to be able to obtain time-varying mean intonation value.

The primary objective of the vibrato model is to accurately capture intonation variations in sustained musical notes while eliminating the influence of vibrato. This separation enables us to isolate and analyze the intrinsic intonation fluctuations in

long notes, providing valuable insights for our research. That is the main reason why this model will then be used in both long and short notes.

Even though vibrato is a characteristic ornament of notes with a greater duration, it can be found on short notes too. For this matter, for every trimmed pitch bend independently of its length, if after analyzing its main frequency it was detected to be between 4-10Hz, standard range for vibrato, it would be treated as a vibrato note. Vibrato notes' mean pitch value will be calculated as the average value of the calculated time-varying mean of the interpolated series calculated from the positive and negative peaks.

The application of this method lead us to different results that will be commented on the result section in comparison to not applying that model to short notes.

Chapter 5

Results

The main goal of this project is to model recurrent intonation issues related to psycho-acoustics that might have an implication in the way that humans listen to sounds and understand intonation and music. In this chapter we will describe the outcomes of this intonation analysis project.

5.1 Short notes intonation deviation analysis

After grouping into tonalities all intonation deviation values per note we are headed to calculate different statistic parameters per tonality and scale degree that might define the intonation variation in the selected studies.

Different statistics like the mean, standard deviation (Std) and median will be taken into consideration and the results will be showed in specific figures. These figures include the intonation deviation (in cents) from the 12-TET across 5 Major tonalities (C Major, G Major, A Major, F Major and Eb Major). Roman numerals represent the note grades such as tonic (I), mediant (III), dominant (V), etc. The tables on the left show the direct intonation deviations, while the tables on the right show the intonation deviations normalized with respect to the tonic (tonic normalization).

In the following page is possible to see the mentioned figures, that can be consulted in the Appendix for a better readability.

In general, it is complicated to observe negative deviations from 12-TET, except in some cases within the I and IV degrees without tonic normalization. Once normalized with respect to the tonic, the negative mean deviation is mostly focused on the subdominant (IV).

The mean (Figure 15, top) and median (Figure 15, middle) for all cases suggest that the violinists play the mediant (III) and leading tone (VII) sharper than the 12-TET, whereas the tonic (I) and subdominant (IV) are the closest to the values in 12-TET.

Tonic normalization gives the chance to see that grade III deviation is around 4.8-6.25 cents above the tonic mean intonation deviation from 12-TET, independently of the tonality (Figure 15, top right). VII grade intonation deviation also falls in a similar range (3.17-6.19 cents) regardless of the key (Figure 15, top right).

If instead of the mean plots we take a look at the median plots (Figure 15, middle), the tendencies are even stronger than on the previous tables. It's also possible to observe that for the median intonation deviation, A Major tends to be flatter than other tonalities for all scale degrees except for III and VII after tonic normalization.

The standard deviations (Figure 15, bottom) can be viewed as the representation of the stability of these intonation choices. They mostly change with the difficulty of the key on the violin, e.g., the keys with more accidentals (A Major and Eb Major) are harder to play in a stable intonation when compared to keys with less accidentals as for example G Major or F Major. Overall, the dominant (V) will have relatively small standard deviation values, constituting one of the most stable scale degrees regarding intonation choices, while for the leading tone (VII) it will be possible to see a broader variation, this is, less stability on the intonation choices with respect to 12-TET values.

Figure 15: Mean (top), Median (middle) and STD (bottom) Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes without (left) and with (right) tonic normalization in cents

Similar intonation patrons can also be observed in scale degrees for different octaves, as the next figure shows (Figure 16). Major sharp intonation deviation from 12-TET will be noted for III and IV grades, specially in the 5th octave. It is possible to consult Figure 16 in appendix too, for better readability.

Figure 16: Intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes in the three octaves without tonic normalization

Figure 17: Intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents in a larger subset containing other grades excluded in the previous controlled study

These variations have been also generalized to other etudes of the Wohlfahrt method, that not necessarily meet the conditions of first position and no accidentals of the

seven selected etudes for this study (Figure 17). For these etudes, the first 30 etudes of the Wohlfahrt Op45 method, we observe the same tendency among studied tonalities: sharper III and VII grades with respect to 12-TET, as well as I and IV grades close to the 12-TET values.

5.2 Vibrato influence on short notes intonation

As we mentioned on previous chapters, the vibrato model application on short notes as a tool to accurately capture intonation variations in sustained musical notes. In the case of short notes, it took two different cases: considering vibrato only on long notes (Case A) and considering vibrato in both short and long notes (Case B).

Case A will have a 66.79% coverage value and Case B will have a 66.66%.

The main results of both cases can be consulted on Figure 18, where we can appreciate a similar tendency, seeing that the application of the vibrato model to the short notes is not statistically significant.

Figure 18: Mean Intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes - Case A (left) Vibrato model application on short notes. Case B (right) Non vibrato model application on short notes

5.3 Long notes intonation deviation analysis

For long notes, the process of segmentation included the application of the vibrato model for the cases whose highest frequency computed via rFFT was in the range 4-10 Hz. This vibrato model will assure an accurate intonation deviation capture for notes with that type of ornament. For the notes that didn't meet that specific criteria they have been applied the histogram workflow. Long notes coverage will reach with a 95.43%.

Table 6: Number of long notes per tonality (all players)

	C Major	G Major	F Major	A Major	Eb Major
I	14	6	7	4	6
III	-	7	-	-	-

As we can see on Table 6, the long notes correspond to the tonic (I), with an exception for G-III in one etude (No26), which deviates more from the 12-TET compared to the tonics (Table 7).

Table 7: Mean Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for long notes [cents]

	C Major	G Major	F Major	A Major	Eb Major
I	3.62	1.53	0.89	2.07	0.41
III	-	7.52	-	-	-

It is also important to note in Table 7 the difference in the intonation deviation for the tonic across tonalities, that goes from 0.41 cents for Eb Major to 3.62 cents in the case of C Major.

5.4 Intonation deviations from 12-TET across tonalities

Knowing that we are working with tonalities with different numbers and types of accidentals, and after taking a look at previous results, we developed the hypothesis that intonation differences also depend on the tonality each etude was played.

To prove that hypothesis we calculated the STD, which in this case we will understand as the notes' stability, and did a simple test: was there any difference on the stability of the notes if we considered scale degrees (SD) and organized the notes around them before the calculations, compared to the results of the overall variance of the notes intonation without taking into consideration the scale degrees organization?

Table 8: Tonalities difference in intonation from the 12-TET [cents]

	C Major	G Major	F Major	A Major	Eb Major
Without SDs	6.35	5.94	4.94	7.08	7.08
With SDs	4.70	4.05	3.16	5.88	6.02

As we can see on Table 8, the data suggest that our hypothesis is true, as the overall variance within the scale (this is, without considering SDs) is for all cases higher than the variance for every scale degree. As we've seen, if these two intonation deviations (with and without SDs) would be part of the same normal distribution, their variance should remain the same or similar when we control it with respect to a variable (with SD) and should be different when we don't (without SD).

5.5 Direction effects on intonation deviations from 12-TET for short notes

The note prior to the goal note might have a lot to say about intonation deviation. This is what we are calling direction. By knowing if the pitch of the note before the note whose intonation deviation we're taking into consideration was higher or lower than the goal note's pitch we try to see if there is actually some kind of pattern to look for while considering the hand position and string that we might have come to the hand position we are actually in.

Direction has already been studied by several authors in the last century [7, 55, 24]. Greene stated that "upward and downward progression of the intervals had no measurable effect upon either the direction or the extent of their typical deviation from the theoretical scale values" for unaccompanied violinists [7], but a couple studies from Madsen contradict this theory. Madsen concludes that "vocalists, violinists, and trombonists who descend a harmonic minor scale, perform with much greater pitch acuity than do those who ascend the scale" in unaccompanied performances [55]. Years later another study from Madsen concluded that for unaccompanied performances, vocal pitch acuity is superior when descending, rather than ascending, the C or D scale [56].

Yet, the current case we are studying differs from the conditions of the mentioned studies as it takes place studying seven different artists in only major keys while playing melodies and not isolated intervals or scales.

Considering the strictly subsequent note, we might have three different types of directions: Ascendent, Descendent or Equal. In Table 9 we can find the distribution for the directions per scale degree.

In the next pages we can see the tables corresponding to the mean and STD for all three considered directions: ascending, descending and equal. For each page it is possible to see the intonation deviation (in cents) from the 12-TET across 5 Major tonalities. Roman numerals represent the note grades: tonic (I), dominant (V), etc.

Table 9: Direction per scale degree all etudes

	First Note	Ascending	Descending	Equal
I	3	126	153	39
II	0	88	99	42
III	0	122	153	39
IV	0	85	83	31
V	2	95	153	34
VI	1	78	67	32
VII	1	54	110	35

There are six tables on each page (Figures 19 and 20): each row will contain a different direction: Ascending on the top, Descending on the middle and Equal at the bottom. The tables on the left show the direct intonation deviations, while the tables on the right show the intonation deviations normalized with respect to the tonic (tonic normalization). It is important to note that Equal direction only exists on No15, whose tonality is C Major, so for the couple tables at the bottom only one row will be available.

The existence of two accidentals concentrated on the fifth bar of the etude No11 is reason why for the descending direction a new column featuring $\#IV$ appears (Figures 19 and 20, middle). As these two accidentals are so near and are only present in one bar of the etude, we will still take the etude information into consideration for this study.

In Figure 19 it is possible to observe the maintenance of the trend previously observed, that suggests that the violinists play the mediant (III) and leading tone (VII) sharper than the 12-TET, whereas the tonic (I) and subdominant (IV) are the closest to the values in 12-TET. This trend is seen accross different tonalities and different directions.

Regarding the stability of the intonation choices, which can be seen in Figure 20, it is possible to note that they follow similar patterns to those found in Figure 15: they mostly change with the difficulty of the key on the violin, having the dominant (V) as one of the most stable scale degrees in comparison to 12-TET and the leading tone (VII) as one of the least stable grades.

Figure 19: Mean Intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes for different directions Ascending (top), Descending (middle) and Equal (bottom), without (left) and with (right) tonic normalization

Figure 20: Standard Deviation in intonation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes for different directions Ascending (top), Descending (middle) and Equal (bottom), without (left) and with (right) tonic normalization

5.5.1 Ascending vs Descending direction

Mean intonation deviation

When comparing directions, it is possible to see that overall they follow a pretty similar tendency: sharper mediants (III) and leading tones (VII) from 12-TET values, and stable around 12-TET reference values for tonic (I) and subdominant (IV). Although there might be some sharper intonation deviation values for the ascending direction, those deviations from descending direction won't differ in a statistically significant way.

Figure 21: Mean intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes for Ascending (left) and Descending (right) directions, with (bottom) and without (top) tonic normalization

STD intonation deviation

In the case of the deviation, the results are similar to the mean intonation deviation ones, as the overall image doesn't declare a huge difference between the two directions, as if there are some deviations they are usually less than 1.5 cents (for descending notes the STD for the VII and IV grade is sharper than for ascending notes), they won't be of statistical significance.

Figure 22: STD intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes for Ascending (left) and Descending (right) directions, with (bottom) and without (top) tonic normalization

Chapter 6

Discussion

Ambrazevičius writes about the systematic deviations of an actual live performance from a mechanically precise one, also called "performance rules" [57]. Subconscious rules that every musician applies making scores differ from appropriate performance of the given style.

Considering a small subset of Wohlfahrt Op45 studies we have analyzed the relation of each scale degree to its reference intonation value, reaching the ideas exposed in the fifth chapter and that we will analyze in this one.

In an overview of the main results it's possible to note a general tendency along the outcomes of this study. While it is rare to find negative values, most deviations are upwards from the correct intonation (12-TET for Western Classical Music). According to the literature, these intonation phenomena are called contraction (or flatness) and stretching (or sharpness).

As we have mentioned, it is possible to see on our results that the mediant and leading note (III and VII grades) are usually sharper than 12-TET while I and IV are usually near the 12-TET reference value or even flatter at times. These results are consistent with previous studies as E. Terhardt and M. Zick research on the Evaluation of the Tempered Tone Scale in Normal, Stretched, and Contracted Intonation [58] or Sogin's studies where he claimed that all string instruments tend

to be sharper than the 12-TET reference intonation values [40].

In E. Terhardt and M. Zick work, which consisted on sound tests, they conclude that on average, stretched intonation was evaluated as worst in test sounds IV and VI, explaining that the harmonics of the constituent complex tones form a really complex spectral pattern in each of these sound's chord. At the same time, the total average preferred test sound for I, II and V was the stretched one, while for IV was the contracted. The VII grade wasn't studied.

The mean intonation deviation values reach its maximum near 9.5 cent and its minimum around -0.35 cent, which are in between the suggested range of mistuning perceptibility proposed by Madsen, Edmonson, and Madsen in 1969 [59], who find a threshold of about 10 cents, while earlier, in 1942, Williamson claimed a threshold as low as 2 cents [60].

If we compare the difference between 12-TET intonation system and Just Intonation (Table 1, page 8) we will be able to note that the intonation deviation that our results show might be a combination between the flexibility both intonation systems and also the main intonation differences between them. Modern studies suggest that musicians while trying to stick to defined intonation systems with accompaniment have mean deviations of 4.9 cents (SD = 6.5 cents) in the equal-temperament condition and of 6.7 cents (SD = 8.1 cents) in the just-intonation condition [61]. In fact, several have suggested that, while violin intonation didn't fit any tuning system, the closest one was the Pythagorean [38, 33, 30].

As we have selected a subset of monophonic Major etudes, we will restrict our comments to major intervals. As the majority of the consulted bibliography takes into consideration intervals instead of scale degrees, for a better reference we've normalized the values around the tonic value (tonic normalization). In that way, we can compare those results, agreeing with several authors like Greene, Nickerson and Geringer that had already noted expansion or sharpness with respect to 12-TET values in second and third major intervals, among others [38, 30, 33], being III and VII grades the sharpest grades we've found with respect to 12-TET in our project.

It has not been possible to find any paper mentioning the tuning of the seventh degree or, failing that, of the seventh interval (neither major nor minor).

In the case of the Major sixth, the results we are obtaining doesn't necessarily match the ones Just Intonation and 12-TET suggest and that we initially expected. While it is true that in the case of the submediant (VI) we've encountered sharpness in comparison with 12-TET reference values, agreeing with the consulted bibliography [33, 32], we expected to see a much more significant deviation. It is possible to note when comparing intonation systems as 12-TET and Just Intonation (Table 1, page 8), where Major Sixth has the greatest intonation difference of all intervals. Taking a look at standard intonation for the mentioned scale degree we can see great variability, specially for keys with high accidental numbers as A Major and Eb Major.

In the case of the subdominant (IV grade), the results totally agree with what we have seen in bibliography [30] and intonation system comparison tables (Tables 1 and 2, pages 8 and 9). The fourth grade is one of the most stable scale degrees, staying very close to 12-TET theoretical values.

Still, we can't forget about the fact that intonation may be affected by many other factors such as hand position and fingering. The harmonics of the constituent complex tones and the strong interaction of adjacent simultaneous spectral components may partly explain this type of phenomena.

In fact, we've seen some kind of relationship between the use of certain fingers to play III and VII grades in contrast to I and IV. As one of the characteristics of the selected etudes is that they are played in the first position and as they are technical etudes, we can know that certain notes are going to be played with specific fingers from the left hand. More precisely we can know that what violinists call first (index finger), second (middle finger) and third (ring finger) finger and also half position (1st finger low) are going to be in place.

After doing the proper calculations we've seen that for all tonalities, there is a prevalence on the use of the first (index) finger for the most unstable grades (III

and VII) and a prevalence for the second (middle) finger for the most stable ones (I and IV). If we divide this per octaves it's possible to see a 40% prevalence of the first finger (index) for the III degree in the octave C4-C5 and the same prevalence for the second finger (middle) for the tonic in the C5-C6 octave.

Although this may only be a very small part of the explanation, and in specific for this instrument, we are sure that hand positioning for both left and right hands, and biomechanics play an important role in intonation for string instruments, far beyond fingering, and involve different forces coming from muscular and tendon structures that can be generalized in future specific studies or that can also be exclusive for each instrumentalist, taking into account his composition.

Left hand position but also intonation perception itself might be heavily influenced by note direction. With a mean maximum jump between notes of 10.57 semitones while ascending and 8.14 semitones while descending, as we can see in the plots included in the previous chapters, the direction can cause, in a more or less subtle way, the intonation deviation to vary. Regarding the violin technique, this fact may be linked with the presence or absence of physical references when going up and down, and also, with the presence of the semitones inside of the scale.

While it is clear that the general tendency is followed independently regardless of the direction, the slight differences that could make us think that for ascending directions the deviation is somewhat greater, are not statistically significant. The literature review also wasn't clear about this phenomenon, suggesting sharper intonation for descending sequences [26, 40] but also contradicting that statement [38].

Within the whole family of stringed instruments, and of course also for the violin, the absence of physical markings indicating the position of one note or another has always been both an advantage and a disadvantage.

On the one hand, as far as intonation is concerned, it makes it a totally versatile instrument, capable of making the tuning more flexible in order to transform it into a pleasant musical experience for our acoustic perception system, regardless of the "correct" value of the tuning.

On the other hand, the absence of references can play a trick on even the most experienced violinist. It has been indicated that the perception of sharpness is less accurate than flatness discrimination, particularly for old more musically experienced subjects [29].

The presence of the semitones inside of the scale also plays with references, since contraction is usually associated with smaller intervals [62] and two notes separated by a semitone will always be played close together in Western Classical music, obtaining an immediate reference when going up and making it cognitively possible to believe that those two fingers should be closer than expected when going down, or even over-correcting any kind of intonation mistake.

Still, for a clear look at intonation deviation, we should always consider the variation of the results, that STD gives us. As we can see, standard deviation doesn't follow a really clear pattern, although its maximum values are placed on the III, VI and VII grade, and predominantly on the A Major and Eb Major tonalities. This scale degree placement may have some relation with both the general tendency and the indications from the bibliography. The different consulted studies claim that, when general consistent tendencies are found, individual variability still plays an important role [28]. After all, we are studying something as subjective and personal as music.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

In this master thesis we have studied a selected sample of classical etudes from Wohlfahrt Op45. In order to assure the reliability of this process, the workflow consisted of different stages of preprocessing with MUSC, clustering and note segmentation in order to work with the most stable part of the signal, i.e. each of the pitch bends. A vibrato reconstruction model was also built in order to be able to differentiate between intonation choices and ornamentation, specially on long notes. The score figure value was followed in order to classify notes according to duration.

While these etudes being monophonic, in a major key with no modulations and played in first position, assuring the non influence of position shifting on intonation deviation, it was possible to observe general tendencies among the results that agree with the consulted literature. Classifying the played notes by scale degrees it is possible to see sharp intonation deviations from 12-TET on III and VII degrees while I and IV grades are usually more stable towards the reference 12-TET intonation values. It has been taken into consideration the vibrato influence and direction effects on short notes, noting that for short notes, the vibrato influence wasn't statistically significant. The differences between ascending and descending note intonation values were considered statistically insignificant.

Looking back at the original research questions, we've contributed to the intonation analysis field with an automatized approach that has helped us to model changes

and choices in intonation with musical issues as scale degrees and tonalities, which might have an implication in the way that humans listen and understand intonation. This automatized perspective differs from the usual intonation deviation assessment which rely on manual or semi-automatic pitch and note transcription software as Elan or Tony.

To sum up, it is safe to say that intonation is a flexible concept that is not determined by abstract tuning systems but the result of several interactions among musical instrument acoustics, biomechanics, musical context, compositional features and deviation patterns for specific scale degrees and intervals.

7.1 Limitations and Future Work

Further research should consider the following limitations of this master thesis:

- New etude/caprice/song subsets analysis, consider other types of key scales (Minor, Pentatonic, etc.)
- Open the research to other instruments and music styles and genres. While these results are focused on Western Classical music, other types of music genres might have specific relations for intonation and scale degrees.
- Stable part trimming: while this work has taken multiple steps for reliable intonation analysis, the processing of some pitch bends, especially oval-shaped bends, can support segmentation enhancements. The use of confidences, soft predictions, might be an interesting option for future work. In the future this might be improved by making the analysis part of the MUSC algorithm before generating predictions.
- Further research into short/long note consideration. As we've seen, artistically, different lengths might be attributed to notes with a theoretical same duration.
- Fingering and hand position. While this work consists on the analysis of the pitch bends, a dataset that includes both video and audio would be a really

insightful idea to see what type of influence does the hand positioning into intonation and differentiate motor and cognitive level for playing.

7.2 Reproducibility

The main code and results of this project is available in GitHub.

You will find the main functions developed to implement this project in order to arrive at the results demonstrated in Chapter 4:

- Note segmentation and processing
- The vibrato model
- Note clustering
- Intonation deviation from 12-TET heatmaps for both short and long notes
- Intonation deviation from 12-TET heatmaps for both short notes regarding backwards and forwards direction

In the `main_functions` folder you can find the functions that were developed throughout the project and that have applied through the different files. This is the link:

https://github.com/perezrmaria/intonation_analysis

The analyzed recordings can be found on the dataset from Tamer et al [17]

<https://github.com/MTG/violin-transcription/tree/main/dataset>

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Appendices

.1 Appendix

In this appendix some of the most commented figures are featured for a better readability, in specific:

- Mean Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes without tonic normalization in cents
- Mean Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes with tonic normalization in cents
- STD Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes without tonic normalization in cents
- STD Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes with tonic normalization in cents
- Intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes in the three octaves without tonic normalization

Figure 23: Mean Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes without tonic normalization in cents

Figure 24: Mean Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes with tonic normalization in cents

Figure 25: STD Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes without tonic normalization in cents

Figure 26: STD Intonation deviation from the 12-TET for short notes with tonic normalization in cents

Figure 27: Intonation deviation from the 12-TET in cents for short notes in the three octaves without tonic normalization